

COMPARISON OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MCKENZIE EXTENSION EXERCISES VERSUS SWISS BALL EXERCISES ON PAIN, LUMBAR ROM AND FUNCTIONAL DISABILITY AMONG SUBJECTS WITH PIVD

**M.SAI VENNELA ¹, Dr.G. KAMESWARI MPT (Neurology) ²,
Dr.V.SRIKUMARI MPT (Neurology)³, Dr .K.MADHAVI, MPT(Cardio
thoracic) Ph.D, FIAP ⁴**

1. MPT (Neurology), COP, SVIMS, Tirupati. 2. Assistant Professor, COP, SVIMS,
Tirupati. 3. Associate Professor, COP, SVIMS. 4. Professor & Principal,
COP, SVIMS, Tirupathi.

ABSTRACT

Introduction:

A Prolapsed Intervertebral Disc (PIVD), often called a lumbar disc herniation (LDH), is a common reason for lower back pain and sciatica, affecting many adults around the world. It happens when the soft inner part of a spinal disc pushes out through a weakened outer layer, pressing on nearby nerves. This pressure can lead to pain, stiffness in the lower back, and difficulty doing everyday activities .

Aim:

To know and compare the effectiveness of McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises on pain, Lumbar Range of Motion and Functional disability among subjects with PIVD.

Method:

Thirty subjects were included in the study selected on the basis of inclusion, exclusion criteria and the subjects were assigned into two groups i.e., Group A and Group B after obtaining informed consent from the subjects. McKenzie extension exercises were given to GROUP A and Swiss ball exercises were given to GROUP B. TENS and stretchings were given to bilateral hamstring muscles and calf muscles to both the groups in common. Cryotherapy and kneading were given to the patients with paraspinal muscle spasm. Both the groups were treated for 4 sessions in a week for 3 weeks. Numerical pain rating scale was used to assess the pain, modified Schober's index was used to assess the lumbar ROM and Oswestry disability index was used to

assess the functional disability.

Results:

The descriptive statistics indicate that both Group A and Group B had similar participant characteristics, with mean ages of 41 and 41.27 years respectively, and an identical average PIVD duration of 2.27 months. Within-group analysis showed that both groups experienced significant improvements post-intervention. In Group A, pain (NPRS) scores reduced from 7.47 to 3.87, disability (ODI) scores from 20.87 to 13.60, and lumbar ROM (Modified Schober's Index) increased from 1.20 cm to 3.07 cm, all with highly significant p values (<0.0001). Similarly, Group B showed reductions in pain (7.53 to 5.13), disability (20.87 to 13.60), and increased ROM (1.33 cm to 3.60 cm), with p value < 0.0001 . Between-group comparisons revealed that Group A had significantly greater reductions in pain ($p = 0.048$) and functional disability ($p = 0.001$), while Group B showed significantly greater improvement in lumbar ROM ($p = 0.037$).

Conclusion:

The present study concludes that both McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises are effective in reducing pain and functional disability, as well as improving lumbar range of motion (ROM). However, when compared, McKenzie extension exercises are more effective in reducing pain and functional disability, while Swiss ball exercises are more beneficial for increasing lumbar ROM.

Key words: PIVD, McKenzie extension exercises, Swiss ball exercises, Numerical Pain Rating Scale, Modified Schober's Index, Oswestry Disability Index

INTRODUCTION

Lower back pain is the leading cause of disability worldwide, placing a significant strain on individuals, healthcare services, and society as a whole. One of the most well-known conditions linked to lower back issues is radiculopathy resulting from lumbar disc herniation (LDH) (1). A Prolapsed Intervertebral Disc (PIVD), often called a lumbar disc herniation, is a common reason for lower back pain and sciatica, affecting many adults around the world. It happens when the soft inner part of a spinal disc pushes out through a weakened outer layer, pressing on nearby nerves. This pressure can lead to pain, stiffness in the lower back, and difficulty doing everyday activities (2).

Earlier studies have shown that about 5% of adults aged 30 and older have symptoms of LDH at any given time, with the rates differing by age and gender. Among people between 25 and 55 years old, most herniated discs with symptoms around 95% are found in the lower part of the spine, especially at the L4-L5 and L5-S1 levels (1).

Disc compression can be caused by both external and internal factors. External causes include physical injuries, which are commonly seen in athletes, labourers, porters, and trekkers. Internal factors such as smoking can speed up disc degeneration. Studies on animals have shown that smoking may increase inflammation, damage the outer part of the disc, reduce blood flow, and interfere with how nutrients reach the disc, all of which contribute to disc problems (3).

The primary signs and symptoms of LDH include lower back pain that extends down to the back of the thigh and leg, along with numbness and tingling sensations in the areas of skin supplied by the affected nerve. Patients may also experience muscle weakness and reduced reflexes in the corresponding muscle groups.

Various treatment options are available for patients with LDH, ranging from conservative approaches to surgical procedures. When symptoms are present, initial treatment typically includes conservative methods such as behavioural therapy, physical therapy, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), oral steroids, and epidural steroid injections. Surgery is usually considered if these treatments do not provide sufficient relief. However, surgical outcomes are not always better than non-surgical options. Although surgery can offer quicker symptom relief, its long-term benefits are still debated. There is also a risk of nerve related complications during surgery, and some patients may continue to experience numbness and pain afterward due to nerve irritation.

Recently, to minimize the risks of surgery and support tissue healing, researchers have been exploring the safety and effectiveness of new treatments. These include physiochemically active therapies such as platelet-rich plasma (PRP), bone marrow aspirate concentrate (BMAC) cell therapy, and low-intensity pulsed ultrasound (LIPUS).

Conservative physiotherapy is still the main method used to treat PIVD, with exercise therapy playing a key role in the recovery process (4). Electrotherapy methods like TENS, IFT, ultrasound, low-level laser therapy, decompression therapy and traction are commonly used to relieve pain in people with PIVD (5,6). The most common physiotherapy interventions for LBP extension biased include traction, stabilization, manipulation and McKenzie exercises. The manual treatment techniques such as joint mobilization is commonly given intervention applied for spinal dysfunction patients such as the McKenzie approach, Maitland mobilization, neural tissue mobilization, Mulligan's mobilization and soft tissue interventions. McKenzie exercises centralize pain, decrease functional disability, and improve spinal mobility. Swiss ball exercises are stabilization

exercises that strengthen core muscles, decrease pain perception, increase trunk mobility, decrease functional disability and improve spinal mobility (7). The McKenzie method, also known as Mechanical Diagnosis and Therapy (MDT), is a widely used approach in physical therapy. This method emphasizes patient education and active participation, guided by a trained therapist. According to McKenzie, self-treatment is the most effective way to achieve long-term relief from back and neck pain. The technique primarily focuses on extension-based exercises, including gentle manipulations, movement-based routines, and posture correction strategies. These exercises are often referred to as self-directed or self-manipulation exercises and can be used to manage pain and improve posture at various stages of recovery. If a patient experiences increased leg pain during the exercises, the treatment should be paused. The intensity of exercises should be gradually increased, depending on the individual's tolerance and progress.

Swiss ball exercises are commonly used by physical therapists as part of core stability training. They are more effective than exercises performed on a stable surface, as the ball adds an element of instability that challenges the body. These exercises help strengthen the abdominal and back muscles and are useful in treating problems such as poor balance, weak pelvic floor muscles, muscle spasms, and stress. Swiss ball routines are also often included as a warm-up to improve muscle flexibility, which can reduce strain on the back. In gym workouts, they enhance overall body flexibility. People who practice yoga may also benefit from Swiss ball exercises, as they help improve joint mobility and reduce the risk of injury (8).

AIM OF THE STUDY

To know and compare the effectiveness of McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises on pain, Lumbar Range of Motion and Functional disability among subjects with PIVD.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To evaluate the efficacy of McKenzie extension exercise on Pain by Numerical pain rating scale (NPRS), on Lumbar Range of Motion by Modified Schober's Index (MSI), on Functional disability by Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) in subjects with PIVD
2. To evaluate the efficacy of Swiss ball exercises on Pain by Numerical pain rating scale (NPRS), on Lumbar Range of Motion by Modified Schober's Index (MSI), on Functional disability by Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) in subjects with PIVD
3. To compare the efficacy of McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises on pain by Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), on Lumbar Range of Motion by Modified Schober's Index (MSI), on functional disability by Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) in subjects with PIVD

METHODOLOGY

Materials:

Following materials were used for the evaluation and intervention

Swiss ball – for the subjects of height less than 155cm, the ball size used was 45cm; for 156 – 165 cm it was 55cm; for 165 – 178cm, it was 65cm; and for more than 178cm, it was 75cm, Low couch, Pillows, TENS, Inch tape

Methods:

- Study design: Randomized control trial
- Sampling technique: purposive sampling method

- Sample size: N = 30 subjects (Group A (n) = 15 subjects, Group B(n) = 15 subjects)
- Sampling method: By simple randomization technique – lottery method
- Study settings: College of physiotherapy, Arogyasree ward, SVIMS, Tirupati, Sri Venkateswara Ayurvedic Hospital, Tirupati.
- Study duration: 6 months
- Treatment duration: - 4 Session /week for a total duration of - 3 weeks
- Ethical approval code: (Roc.No.AS/11/IEC/SVIMA/2017) **IEC No.1775**,
- Clinical Trail Registration India (CTRI) ID: CTRI/2025/06/088877

Inclusion criteria:

- Subjects of age group – 25 to 45 years
- Both males and females
- PIVD grade 1 and grade 2
- Prolapsed disc with radiating pain to one lower limb
- Duration of low back pain is from 1 to 3 months
- Subjects of Oswestry disability score – 15 to 34
- Subjects who had not previously undergone exercises specifically abdominal strengthening, spinal stabilization, or manipulation since the onset of their condition.

Exclusion criteria:

- If underwent any recent spinal surgery or advised for surgery
- Subjects with LBP of duration less than one month and more than 3 months
- Subjects with any renal diseases
- Subjects with spinal conditions like tumors, spondylolisthesis, infection and spinal fracture, spinal tuberculosis.
- Inflammatory joint disease such as rheumatoid arthritis
- Pregnancy
- General health problems which prevent from participating in an exercise program

Intervention

The study was performed after getting approval from IEC No. 1775 and CTRI reg no (CTRI/2025/06/088877). All the subjects who met the inclusion criteria were included in the study after explaining the procedure. Written informed consent was then obtained from the subjects. The subjects were allocated into 2 groups in 1:1 ratio with 15 in each group.

Group A (McKenzie extension exercises)	Group B (Swiss ball exercises)
McKenzie extension exercises 1 session/day – with 5 repetitions each with a 10 sec hold and with a rest interval of 10 sec	Swiss ball exercises 1 session / day – with each position 5 repetitions with a 10 sec hold and with a rest interval of 10 sec
TENS – Model no: 3809 Low TENS 35 Hz frequency duration of 150 μ sec. for 20 min	TENS – Model no: 3809 Low TENS 35 Hz frequency duration of 150 μ sec. for 20 min
Passive stretchings – for bilateral hamstrings and calf muscles - 3 repetitions 30 sec hold time 10 sec relax	Passive stretchings – for bilateral hamstrings and calf muscles- 3 repetitions 30 sec hold time 10 sec relax
Treatment duration – 1 hr /session, weekly – 4 days, for 3 weeks	Treatment duration – 1 hr /session, weekly – 4 days, for 3 weeks

Treatment Protocol

A. Experimental group – A (McKenzie exercises)

Prone Lying: The subjects adopted the prone lying position with the arms alongside the trunk and the head turned to one side. This position was maintained for 10 seconds initially. Next, the subjects were made to lie prone on their elbows.

Prone on Elbows: The subjects, already lying prone, placed their elbows under their shoulders and raised the upper half of their body, leaning on their elbows and forearms while keeping the pelvis and thighs on the couch. The subjects held that position for 10 seconds. Next, the subjects were made to perform prone press-ups from the prone- on-elbows position.

Prone press-ups: The subjects lay on their stomachs with their palms placed near their shoulders. They slowly pushed their shoulders up, keeping their hips on the surface and allowing their back to extend. Next, the subjects were made to perform prone arm/leg raises from the prone press-up position.

Prone Arm/Leg Raises: The subjects lay on their stomachs on the mat, keeping their neck aligned with their spine and their arms and legs outstretched overhead. They gradually raised one arm and the leg on the same side. The position was held for 10 seconds before slowly returning to the starting position.

Next, the subjects were made to perform the prone lying Superman extension exercise from the prone arm/leg raise position.

Prone Lying Superman’s Extension exercise: The subjects lay on the floor in prone position, with their legs straight and arms extended. Keeping their head in a neutral position,

they slowly lifted their arms and legs off the floor, or until they felt their lower back muscles contracting, and held the position for 10 seconds.

Next, the subjects were made to perform standing extension exercises following the prone lying Superman extension exercise.

Standing Extension: While standing, the subjects placed their hands on their back and leaned backward, holding the position for 10 seconds (9).

Each position will be performed for 5 repetitions ,3 sets for 4 days in a week, for 3 weeks
Total treatment duration for exercises – 30 min

b. Experimental group – B (Swiss ball exercises):

Swiss ball exercises can also be used as a supplement to other treatments in order to relieve pain in trunk muscles.

- Straight arm crunch
- Swiss ball alternate arm
- Swiss ball –wall squat
- Swiss ball shoulder bridge
- Swiss ball back extension
- Swiss ball hamstring curl
- Swiss ball leg raise
- A 5-minute warm-up and cool-down protocol was incorporated before and after the interventions to minimize the risk of injury.
- The warm-up and cool-down protocol consisted of a 2-minute walk at an easy pace. (7)
- Each position was repeated five times, with a 20-second hold and a 10-second rest interval between each position.
- Total treatment duration for exercises – 30 min

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Results:

Descriptive statistics:

The study titled Comparison of the effectiveness of McKenzie extension exercises versus Swiss ball exercises on pain, Lumbar ROM and Functional disability among subjects with PIVD included two groups – with 15 participants each. The descriptive statistics for the group – A and group – B provide insights into participate characteristics.

Variables	Group A (Mean ± SD)	Group B (Mean ± SD)
Mean age: years	41.00± 6.46	41.27 ± 6.98
Duration: months	2.27 ± 0.82	2.36 ± 0.78

Table 4: Comparison of Demographic Variables between Group A and Group B
Age distribution was similar across both the groups. On comparison of demographic variables between the groups revealed, in group – A, the mean age was 41 years (SD =

6.46), whereas the group B shows the mean age of 41.27 years (SD = 6.98), indicating that two groups contain same age group participants. The average PIVD duration of PIVD across both the groups have shown similarity with a mean of 2.27 months, SD = 0.82 in group A and mean of 2.36 months, SD = 0.78 in group B.

Table 5: Gender Distribution among Group A and Group B

Gender	Group – A	Group – B
Female	11 (73.33 %)	11 (73.33%)
Male	4(26.67%)	4 (26.67%)
Total (N= 15)	15 (100 %)	15 (100 %)

The gender distribution among participants reveals a predominance of female subjects in both the groups. In the group -A and group -B out of 15 participants, 11 (73.33 %) subjects were females while only 4 (26.67%) subjects were males. Overall, the gender distribution indicates a female dominant sample.

Inferential statistics

Tests of Normality – Shapiro – Wilk test

The Shapiro-Wilk Test is a statistical test used to assess whether a given dataset follows a normal distribution, which is a key assumption for many parametric tests such as the t- test or ANOVA. This test is particularly useful as the study sample size is $N < 50$, making it appropriate for this study. The null hypothesis of the Shapiro-Wilk test is that the data is normally distributed. A p-value less than 0.05 indicates significant deviation from normality, suggesting that the data is not normally distributed.

Table 6: Tests of Normality – Shapiro – Wilk Test

Tests of Normality – Shapiro – Wilk Test			
Outcome measure	Group	Statistic	P – value
NPRS pre	Group A	0.922	0.208
	Group B	0.930	0.271
NPRS post	Group A	0.927	0.246
	Group B	0.936	0.331
Modified Schober’s Index pre	Group A	0.801	0.004
	Group B	0.783	0.002
Modified Schober’s Index post	Group A	0.815	0.006
	Group B	0.761	0.001
ODI pre	Group A	0.901	0.099
	Group B	0.908	0.128
ODI post	Group A	0.901	0.097
	Group B	0.933	0.301

The Shapiro–Wilk test was conducted to assess the normality of outcome variables in both groups. The results indicate a mixed pattern of normality.

NPRS (Numerical Pain Rating Scale): Both pre- and post-intervention scores did not significantly deviate from normality in either group (e.g., Group A pre = 0.922, p = 0.208; Group B pre = 0.930, p = 0.271; Group A post = 0.927, p = 0.246; Group B post =

0.936, $p = 0.331$), indicating normal distribution.

Modified Schober’s Index: Both pre- and post-intervention scores in both groups showed significant deviation from normality (e.g., Group A pre = 0.801, $p = 0.004$; Group B pre = 0.783, $p = 0.002$; Group A post = 0.815, $p = 0.006$; Group B post = 0.761, $p = 0.001$), indicating non-normal distribution.

ODI (Oswestry Disability Index): All p-values were greater than 0.05 (Group A pre = 0.901, $p = 0.099$; Group B pre = 0.908, $p = 0.128$; Group A post = 0.901, $p = 0.097$; Group Bpost = 0.933, $p = 0.301$), indicating normal distribution.

For NPRS and ODI, normality is there. Therefore, Parametric tests (Paired t-test, independent t-test) were used. For Modified Schober’s Index, normality was deviated, so non-parametric tests (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, Mann–Whitney U test).

Table 7: Within group analysis of pre and post mean values of NPRS, ODI and MSI of Group A

Group A (n= 15)						
Outcome measures	Time of test	Mean	SD	t-value	p- value	Test
NPRS	Pre	7.47	1.64	11.22	<0.0001	Paired t-test
	Post	3.87	1.06			
	Mean difference	3.6				
ODI	Pre	20.87	4.96	17.33	<0.0001	Paired t - test
	Post	13.60	4.67			
	Mean difference	7.27				
MSI	Pre	1.20	0.68	0.0	<0.0001	Wilcoxon Signed rank test
	Post	3.07	0.70			
	Mean difference	1.87				

The paired t- test was conducted to evaluate the within group (pre to post intervention) changes in the group A for NPRS and ODI. The results indicate statistically significant improvements in both the outcome measures.

Pain levels, assessed using the Numerical Pain Rating Scale (NPRS), showed a decrease in the mean score from 7.47 before the intervention to 3.87 after. The statistical analysis produced a t-value of 11.22 and a p-value of <0.0001, indicating a highly significant reduction in pain.

For functional disability measured by ODI, the mean score reduced from 20.87 (pre) to 13.60 (post). The test yielded a t-value of 17.33 with a p-value of < 0.0001 indicating a highly significant reduction in functional disability.

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to assess the changes within Group B (from pre- to post-intervention) for the Modified Schober’s Index. The findings revealed a statistically

significant improvement in the outcome measure.

For Lumbar ROM measured by Modified Schober’s Index, the mean score increased from 1.20cm (pre) to 3.07cm (post). The test yielded a w-value of 0.0 with a p value of <0.0001 indicating a highly significant improvement in Lumbar ROM.

Table 8: Within group Analysis of pre and post mean values of NPRS, ODI, and MSI of Group B

Group B (n= 15)						
Outcome measures	Time of test	Mean	SD	t-value	p- value	Test
NPRS	Pre	7.53	1.68	6.87	<0.0001	Paired t-test
	Post	5.13	1.30			
	Mean difference	2.4				
ODI	Pre	24.40	6.42	6.26	<0.0001	Paired t-test
	Post	20.47	4.96			
	Mean difference	3.93				
MSI	Pre	1.33	0.72	0.0	<0.0001	Wilcoxon Signed rank test
	Post	3.60	0.63			
	Mean difference	2.27				

The paired t- test was conducted to evaluate the within group (pre to post intervention) changes in the group B for NPRS and ODI. The results indicate statistically significant improvements in both outcome measures.

- For pain measured by NPRS (Numerical pain rating scale), the mean score reduced from 7.53 (pre) to 5.13 (post). The test yielded a t-value of 6.87 with a p value of <0.0001 indicating a highly significant reduction in pain.
- For functional disability measured by ODI (Oswestry Disability Index), the mean score reduced from 20.87 (pre) to 13.60 (post). The test yielded a t-value of 17.33 with a p-value of < 0.0001 indicating a highly significant reduction in functional disability.

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was used to assess the changes within Group B (from pre- to post-intervention) for the Modified Schober’s Index. The findings revealed a statistically significant improvement in the outcome measure.

- For Lumbar ROM measured by Modified Schober’s Index, the mean score increased from 1.33cm (pre) to 3.60cm (post). The test yielded a w-value of 0.0 with a p value of <0.0001 indicating a highly significant improvement in Lumbar ROM.

Overall, the statistically significant results (i.e., p-values < 0.001) across all measures, supported by meaningful changes in mean values, indicate that McKenzie exercises and Swiss ball exercises led to substantial reduction in pain, function disability and improvement in lumbar ROM in both the groups.

Between group analysis of NPRS, ODI and MSI

Table 9: Between Group Analysis of NPRS, ODI, and MSI of Group A and Group B

Outcome measures	Post mean ± SD		Mean difference	Result	p-value	Statistical Test
	Group A (N=15)	Group B (N=15)				
NPRS	3.87 ± 1.06	5.13 ± 1.30	-1.26	t = - 2.063	0.048*	Independent t-test
ODI	13.60 ± 4.67	20.47 ± 4.96	-6.87	t = - 3.801	0.001**	Independent t-test
MSI	3.07 ± 0.70	3.60 ± 0.63	-0.53	U = 64.0	0.037*	Mann-Whitney U

The independent t-test was conducted to evaluate the between group analysis of NPRS and ODI. Mann-Whitney U test was conducted to evaluate the between group analysis of Modified Schober’s Index. The results indicate statistically significant improvement in outcome measures.

- For pain measured by NPRS, the post mean score of Group A is 3.87 and mean score of Group B is 5.13, with a t – value of -2.063 and with a p value of 0.048 indicating a highly significant reduction of pain in group A than group B.
- For Lumbar ROM measured by Modified Schober’s Index, the post mean score of group A is 3.07 and post mean score of group B is 3.60 with a U value of 64 and with a p value of 0.037 indicating a highly significant improvement of Lumbar ROM in group B than Group A.
- For functional disability measured by ODI, the post mean score of group A is 13.60 and post mean score of group B is 20.47 with a t-value of - 3.801 and with a p-value of 0.001 indicating a highly significant reduction of functional disability in group A subjects than in group B.

Across all outcomes the group A shows significant reduction in pain and functional disability than group B, whereas lumbar ROM is significantly improved in group B than group A, indicating that McKenzie extension exercises were more effective in reducing Pain and Functional disability and Swiss ball exercises are more effective in improving Lumbar ROM.

Discussion

The study compared McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises in treating PIVD -related pain, lumbar ROM, and functional disability. Thirty subjects (aged 25–45) were randomly divided into two groups: group a received McKenzie exercises with conventional physiotherapy, and group b received Swiss ball exercises with conventional physiotherapy for 3 weeks (4 sessions/week). Assessments using NPRS, MSI, and ODI showed significant improvements in both groups. However, group a achieved greater improvement in pain and functional disability, while group b showed better improvement in lumbar ROM.

In this study, Group A’s pain levels (NPRS) decreased from 7.47 ± 1.64 to 3.87 ± 1.06, showing a mean reduction of 3.6. This improvement is likely due to the neuromodulatory effects of McKenzie extension exercises, which reduce central sensitization and activate

descending pain inhibitory pathways. These findings align with Bid et al. (2018), who also reported significant pain reduction with McKenzie exercises (NPRS 7.68 → 0.63, $p < 0.000$), supporting their effectiveness in managing PIVD - related pain. (10)

In this study, Group A's ODI score decreased from 20.87 ± 4.96 to 13.60 ± 4.6 , with a mean improvement of 7.27, indicating reduced functional disability. This improvement is attributed to the mechanical and neurophysiological benefits of McKenzie extension exercises, such as decompression and reduced sensitization. Similar results were reported by Hossain et al. (2021), who found a significant ODI improvement of 32.77 ($p < .001$), further supporting the effectiveness of McKenzie exercises in reducing disability in PIVD patients. (11)

In this study, Group A's MSI score improved from 1.20 ± 0.68 to 3.07 ± 0.70 , with a mean increase of 1.87, indicating enhanced lumbar mobility. This improvement is attributed to McKenzie exercises, which reduce joint and soft-tissue tension, strengthen deep spinal stabilizers, and improve neuromuscular coordination. (12) Similar findings by Al Murdef et al. (2024) showed significant MSI improvement (median 19 → 23, $p < 0.001$), confirming the effectiveness of McKenzie exercises in enhancing lumbar ROM in PIVD patients. (13)

In this study, Group B's NPRS score decreased from 7.53 ± 1.68 to 5.13 ± 1.30 , with a mean reduction of 2.4, indicating pain relief. This improvement is attributed to the activation of deep spinal stabilizers and enhanced proprioception from Swiss ball exercises, which improve trunk coordination and reduce lumbar stress. Similar findings by Jibi Paul et al. (2021) showed a significant VAS reduction ($5.80 \rightarrow 3.20$, $p < 0.0001$), supporting the effectiveness of Swiss ball exercises in alleviating pain in PIVD patients.(14)

In this study, Group B's ODI score decreased from 24.40 ± 6.42 to 20.47 ± 4.96 , showing a mean improvement of 3.93, indicating reduced functional disability. This improvement is attributed to enhanced proprioceptive feedback and neuromuscular coordination from Swiss ball exercises. Similar results by Khokhawala et al. (2019) showed a significant RMQ reduction ($5 \rightarrow 2$, $p < 0.00$), supporting the effectiveness of Swiss ball exercises in reducing functional disability in low back pain patients. (15)

In this study, Group B's MSI score improved from 1.33 ± 0.72 to 3.60 ± 0.63 , showing a mean increase of 2.27, indicating enhanced lumbar ROM. This improvement is due to increased joint and soft tissue mobility, core muscle activation, and better neuromuscular coordination from Swiss ball exercises. Supporting evidence from Frizziero et al. and Jibi Paul et al. (2021) also reported significant lumbar ROM gains, confirming the effectiveness of Swiss ball exercises in improving spinal flexibility in PIVD patients. (13)

The comparison between groups showed that Group A (McKenzie exercises) achieved greater improvements than Group B (Swiss ball exercises). Group A had lower post-treatment pain scores (3.87 vs. 5.13; $t = -2.063$, $p = 0.048$) and significantly better ODI scores (13.60 vs. 20.47; $t = -3.801$, $p = 0.001$). These results support previous studies and meta-analyses indicating that McKenzie exercises provide superior pain reduction and functional improvement due to mechanisms like centralization and repetitive end-range extension. Similar findings by Komal Jamil et al. (2019) also confirmed that McKenzie exercises were more effective than Swiss ball exercises in reducing pain and disability in low back pain patients. (8)

The comparison showed that Group B (Swiss ball exercises) achieved greater improvement in lumbar ROM, with a post-treatment score of 3.60 compared to 3.07 in Group A ($U = 64$, $p = 0.037$). This enhancement is attributed to Swiss ball-based stabilization exercises, which improve spinal stability, balance, flexibility, and neuromuscular control by engaging deep stabilizing muscles through an unstable training surface. (16)

In contrast, the McKenzie Method focuses on spinal extension and directional preference to reduce symptoms by promoting centralization and normalizing disc mechanics. While McKenzie emphasizes specific movement patterns, Swiss ball exercises enhance neuromuscular control and proprioception by challenging the body's stability, which is especially beneficial for improving lumbar mobility and core endurance. (8)

A study comparing Swiss ball and floor-based core exercises found that Swiss ball protocols provided greater gains in flexibility and ROM. This aligns with the present study results, suggesting that unstable-surface training may better facilitate lumbar extension gains. (15)

The study rejects the null hypothesis and accepts the alternate, confirming a significant difference between the two groups in pain, lumbar ROM, and functional disability among PIVD patients. Both McKenzie and Swiss ball exercises were effective overall, but McKenzie exercises produced greater improvements in pain and disability, while Swiss ball exercises resulted in better enhancement of lumbar ROM.

CONCLUSION:

The present study concludes that both McKenzie extension exercises and Swiss ball exercises are effective in reducing pain and functional disability, as well as improving lumbar range of motion (ROM). However, when compared, McKenzie extension exercises are more effective in reducing pain and functional disability, while Swiss ball exercises are more beneficial for increasing lumbar ROM. Hence Null hypothesis is rejected.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- The 3 -Week treatment period is limited, therefore, follow-up studies are suggested to know the long-lasting effects.
- Large sample size is recommended.
- Further research can be done by comparing McKenzie with other advanced treatment strategies such as Telerehabilitation and Vojta therapy.

REFERENCES:

1. Czaprowski D, Afeltowicz A, Gębska M, Pawłowska P, Stolinski L. The influence of physiotherapy with a stabilometric platform on the postural control in patients with low back pain. *J Back Musculoskeletal Rehabil.*
2. Chiu TTW, Hung HC, Lau KT, Chung TK, Wong AY, Cheung SO. Trunk muscle stabilizer activity in patients with disc herniation and healthy subjects during various activities. *Spine*
3. Kaur S. Lumbar prolapsed intervertebral disc & its management. College of Physiotherapy, Adesh University, Bathinda, Punjab. [Internet]. Research Publish Journals
4. Lee JS, Lee SB, Kang KY, Oh SH, Chae DS. Review of recent treatment strategies for lumbar disc herniation (LDH) focusing on nonsurgical and regenerative therapies. *J Clin Med.* 2023
5. Parkhi R, Chitale N, Deshmukh M, Arora SP, Naqvi WM, Phansopkar P. Comprehensive physiotherapy management in PIVD patient.
6. Singh V, Malik M, Kaur J, Kulandaivelan S. A systematic review and meta-analysis on the efficacy of physiotherapy intervention in management of lumbar prolapsed intervertebral disc. *Int J Health Sci (Qassim).* 2021

7. Villarín RR, Marasigan PNR, Cabatay WA, Oarga V, Flores MSE. Swiss ball exercises as an alternative to McKenzie exercises in treating chronic low back pain among poultry workers. *Eur J Mol Clin Med*. 2020.
8. Jamil K, Baqir SR. Comparative effects of McKenzie technique versus Swiss ball exercises along with hot pack in patients with low back pain. *J Rehabil Res*. 2023
9. Sharma J, Kumar N, Kumar S. Comparison of the effectiveness of core strengthening exercise and McKenzie extension exercise on the pain and functional disability in lumbar PIVD condition. *Physiother Occup Ther J*. 2018
10. Bid DD, Soni NC, Yadav AS, Rathod PV. The effects of McKenzie exercises in chronic nonspecific low back pain patients with central sensitization: a pilot study. *J Back Musculoskelet Rehabil*. 2023
11. Hossain MA, Jahid IK, Hossain MF, Uddin Z, Kabir MF, Hossain KMA, Hassan MN, Walton LM. Efficacy of McKenzie Manipulative Therapy on Pain, Functional Activity and Disability for Lumbar Disc Herniation. *Open Sports Sci J*. 2021 jun
12. Mann SJ, Lam JC, Singh P. McKenzie back exercises. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan–. Updated 2023 Jul 3.
13. Al Murdef HSS, Al Jafer FMH, Al Jafer HMH, Alkhamsan SNM, Alyami MSH, Al Sawydan MM, Alsagrei HSM, Alrabaie MA, Abassil AMA, Althobaiti AMN. Comparing the effectiveness of lumbar traction and McKenzie exercises versus McKenzie exercises alone on pain, range of movement and function on individuals with intervertebral disc prolapse. *J Ecohumanism*. 2024
14. Paul J, Indumathi V, Sathya P. Comparative effect of motor control exercise using Swiss ball over stretching exercise on mechanical low back pain. *Int J Physiother*. 2021;8(1):59–63
15. Khokhawala AM, Gaurav R. The effects of lumbar stabilization exercises on a Swiss ball in patients with mechanical low back pain. *Int J Physiotherapy*. 2019
16. Balakrishnan R, Yazid E, Mahat MF. Effectiveness of the core stabilisation exercise on floor and Swiss ball on individuals with non-specific low back pain. *Int J Allied Health Sci*. 2016
17. Hossain MA, Jahid IK, Hossain MF, Uddin Z, Kabir MF, Hossain KMA, Hassan MN, Walton L. Efficacy of McKenzie manipulative therapy on pain, functional activity and disability for lumbar disc herniation.
18. Ozturk B, Gunduz OH, Ozoran K, Bostanoglu S. Effect of continuous lumbar traction on the size of herniated disc material in lumbar disc herniation. *Rheumatol Int* 2006; 26:622-26
19. Roy MH, Anap D. Is McKenzie method with core exercise effective for patients with disc derangement? *VIMS Health Sci J*
20. Pojskic M, Bisson E, Oertel J, Takami T, Zygourakis C, Costa F. Lumbar disc herniation: Epidemiology, clinical and radiologic diagnosis WFNS spine committee recommendations. *World Neurosurg X*. 2024
21. Ravindra VM, Senglaub SS, Rattani A, et al. Degenerative Lumbar Spine Disease: Estimating Global Incidence and Worldwide Volume. *Global Spine Journal*. 2018
22. Singh V, Malik M, Kaur J, Kulandaivelan S, Punia S. A systematic review and meta-analysis on the efficacy of physiotherapy intervention in management of lumbar prolapsed intervertebral disc. *Int J Health Sci (Qassim)*.
23. Hoy D, Bain C, Williams G, March L, Brooks P, Blyth F, Woolf A, Vos T, Buchbinder R. A systematic review of the global prevalence of low back pain. *Arthritis Rheum*. 2012.
24. Kuppuswamy S, George JC, Chemmanam M. Prevalence of lumbar disc herniation and disc degeneration in asymptomatic Indian subjects: an MRI-based study. *Indian J Radiol Imaging*. 2018;28(3):345–9

25. Shetty GM, Jain S, Thakur H, Khanna K. Prevalence of low back pain in India: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Epidemiol Glob Health*. 2022; 14:100956.
26. Azemi ES, Kola I, Kola S, Tanka M. Prevalence of lumbar disk herniation in adult patients with low back pain based on magnetic resonance imaging diagnosis. *J Back Musculoskeletal Rehabil*. 2021;34(5):987–92.
27. Naik HS, Ghosh SN, Saha PK, Biswas P. Quality of life and depressive symptoms in patients with lumbar disc herniation undergoing open discectomy: a 6-month follow-up study from a tertiary care hospital in Eastern India. *Asian J Neurosurg*. 2021;16(4):750–6
28. Khan R, Anwar S, Choudhary A, Saharan AK, Sharma GL. Disability in patients with prolapsed intervertebral disc in lumbar region. *Indian J Orthop*. 2020;54(3):345–50.
29. Hao DJ, Duan K, Liu TJ, Liu JJ, Wang WT. Development and clinical application of grading and classification criteria of lumbar disc herniation. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2017 Nov;96(47): e8676
30. Zielinska N, Podgórski M, Haładaj R, Polguy M, Olewnik Ł. Risk Factors of Intervertebral Disc Pathology-A Point of View Formerly and Today-A Review. *J Clin Med*. 2021 Jan 21;10(3):409
31. Sao K, Risbud MV. Proteoglycan dysfunction: a common link between intervertebral disc degeneration and skeletal dysplasia. *Neurospine*. 2024;21(1):162–78.
32. Hassan MN, Akter P, Hossain MA. Risk factors of prolapse lumbar intervertebral disc (PLID): a synthesis of short review. *Indian J Physiother Occup Ther*. 2022;16
33. Sassack B, Carrier JD. Anatomy, Back, Lumbar Spine. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan–. Updated 2023 Aug 14.
34. Karchevskaya AE, Poluektov YM, Korolishin VA. Understanding Intervertebral Disc Degeneration: Background Factors and the Role of Initial Injury. *Biomedicines*. 2023 Oct 6;
35. Cholewicki J, Juluru K, McGill SM. Intra-abdominal pressure mechanism for stabilizing the lumbar spine. *J Biomech*. 1999 Jan;32(1):13–17. doi:10.1016/S0021- 9290(98)00129-8.
36. Panjabi, Manohar. (1993). The Stabilizing System of the Spine. Part I. Function, Dysfunction, Adaptation, and Enhancement. *Journal of spinal disorders*. 5. 383-9; discussion 397.
37. Dydyk AM, Ngnitewe Massa R, Mesfin FB. Disc Herniation. 2023 Jan 16. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan
38. Huang JS, Fan BK, Liu JM. [Overview of risk factors for failed percutaneous transforaminal endoscopic discectomy in lumbar disc herniation]. *Zhongguo Gu Shang*.
39. Mostofi K, Gharaie Moghaddam B, Karimi Khouzan R, Daryabin M. The reliability of LERI's sign in L4 and L3 radiculalgia. *J Clin Neurosci*.
40. Das JM, Dua A, Nadi M. Straight Leg Raise Test (Lasegue sign) [Internet]. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan–. Updated 6 Oct 2024
41. Wu PH, Kim HS, Jang IT. Intervertebral Disc Diseases PART 2: A Review of the Current Diagnostic and Treatment Strategies for Intervertebral Disc Disease. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020 Mar 20;21(6):2135.
42. Roelofs PD, Deyo RA, Koes BW, Scholten RJ, van Tulder MW. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs for low back pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. Pharmacological management
43. Fu JL, Perlof MD. Pharmacotherapy for spine-related pain in older adults. *Drugs & Aging*. 2022 Jun 27;39
44. Schuttert I, Timmerman H, Petersen KK, McPhee ME, Arendt-Nielsen L, Reneman MF, Wolff AP. The Definition, Assessment, and Prevalence of (Human Assumed) Central Sensitisation in Patients with Chronic Low Back Pain: A Systematic Review

45. Al Qaraghli MI, De Jesus O. Lumbar Disc Herniation [Internet]. In: StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan–. Last update Aug 23, 2023
46. Muniyar K, Darade SB. Effect of Swiss ball training and conventional physiotherapy to improve balance and mobility in post-stroke patients. *Int J Physiotherapy Res.* 2018 Aug;6(4):2813–22. doi:10.16965/ijpr.2018.156.
47. Yoon JS, Lee JH, Kim JS. The effect of Swiss ball stabilization exercise on pain and bone mineral density of patients with chronic low back pain. *J Phys Ther Sci.* 2013;25(8):953–6.
48. Hossain MA, Jahid IK, Hossain MF, Uddin Z, Kabir MF, Hossain KMA, Hassan MN, Walton LM. Effectiveness of McKenzie Manipulative Therapy on Pain, Functional Activity and Disability for Lumbar Disc Herniation. *J Nov Physiother Rehabil.* 2020;4(1):019–27.
49. Al-horani RA, Batainah AS, Shamroukh N, Abumoh'd MF. McKenzie-type exercises improve the functional abilities of a patient with recurrent herniated discs: a case report. *J Rehabil Med Clin Commun.* 2021;4(1):100022.
50. Clare HA, Adams R, Maher CG. A systematic review of efficacy of McKenzie therapy for spinal pain. *Aust J Physiotherapy.* 2009